

(n, π^*) Fluorescence of Pyridazinopyridazine

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Pyridazinopyridazine (2,3,6,7-tetrazanaphthalene) exhibits $^1(n, \pi^*)$ fluorescence in addition to $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ emission. Possible reasons for the slow $^1(n, \pi^*) \rightarrow ^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ ISC rate have been discussed.

THE spectroscopy of azanaphthalenes has been the subject of many investigations¹⁻⁶ in recent years. Their widely varying photophysical properties which are controlled by the ordering and spacing of the singlet and triplet states of different orbital nature. Semiempirical calculations on diazanaphthalenes⁴ having both the nitrogen atoms in the same benzenoid ring show that all are characterised by one $^1(n, \pi^*)$ state below the first $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ state, except phthalazine, where two $^1(n, \pi^*)$ states are calculated to be lowest lying. Hochstrasser *et al.* reinterpreted their earlier observation⁷ of two $^1(n, \pi^*)$ states in phthalazine as one $^1(n, \pi^*)$ state through measurement of dipole moment in the excited state by Stark experiment⁸. In case of the tetrazanaphthalenes (1,3,5,8- and 1,4,5,8-) studied so far, two $^1(n, \pi^*)$ states are predicted below the first $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ state, the second of these lying very close in energy to the $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ state. The experimental support in this regard is, however, lacking. Emission of any tetrazanaphthalene is yet to be reported; diazanaphthalenes (with N-atoms in the same benzenoid ring) are known to emit from their lowest $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ state⁵. Among these, phthalazine's emitting $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ state shows considerable (n, π^*) character owing to strong vibronic coupling with nearby (n, π^*) triplet state⁹. Emission from $^1(n, \pi^*)$ state in these compounds has not been observed. This is in harmony with El-Sayed rule¹⁰ for the inter-system crossing in molecules having the (n, π^*) state as the lowest singlet. According to this rule, if a $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ state occurs below the $^1(n, \pi^*)$ state, the ISC is very fast; otherwise, ISC from the $^1(n, \pi^*)$ state is comparatively slow giving rise to the possibility of $^1(n, \pi^*)$ fluorescence¹¹. There are cases, however, like 9,10-diazaphenanthrene, which exhibit $^1(n, \pi^*)$ fluorescence^{12,13} in spite of having a $^3(n, \pi^*)$ state still lower in energy¹⁴.

We have searched the polyazines for the occurrence of relatively slow $^1(n, \pi^*) \rightarrow ^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ non-radiative transition rate. In this paper, we report the interesting emission spectra of the symmetric compound, 2,3,6,7-tetrazanaphthalene (pyridazinopyridazine, Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Pyridazinopyridazine (atom numbering and axes convention).

Experimental

Pyridazinopyridazine (PP) (a gift from Dr. R. Nesi¹⁴) was purified by sublimation. A mixed crystal in naphthalene was grown from melt using recrystallised and zone-refined naphthalene. No impurity absorption was found in the host crystal above 330 nm. Though earlier attempts⁸ in dissolving other tetrazanaphthalenes in naphthalene failed, we observed a very slight solubility as indicated by the appearance of characteristic absorption bands of the doped species in the spectrum of the mixed crystal. Solvents used were purified and degassed by standard procedures.

The absorption spectra were recorded with a Cary 17D spectrophotometer. The emission and the excitation spectra were recorded with a Perkin-Elmer MPF 44B spectrofluorimeter. The lifetime has been measured using the apparatus described previously¹⁵.

Results

Absorption: Fig. 2 shows the absorption spectra of the compound in different solvents and in the solid state at room temperature. Three distinct transitions having $\lambda_{\max}$ at about 270-290 ($\epsilon \approx 10^4$ in CH_3OH), 330-350 ($\epsilon \approx 130$ in acetone) and 400-420 nm (a hump) have been identified. The

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highest energy band corresponds to the naphthalene $^1(\pi, \pi^*)$ transition, whereas, the low ϵ of the second band and its blue-shift with increasing solvent polarity (Fig. 2) indicates that it is a $S_0 \rightarrow S_1(n, \pi^*)$ transition. Though the position of the $^1(n, \pi^*)$

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra: (1) of solid (reflectance spectrum at 300 K), (2) in acetone, (3) in methanol, (4) in water at 300 K, and (5) of thin mixed crystal (PP doped in naphthalene at 800 K); (a) unpolarised, (b) $E_{\perp}$ to the cleavage plane and (c) $E_{\parallel}$ to the cleavage plane.

state is almost similar to that observed in phthalazine ($\lambda_{max} = 356$ nm with $\epsilon = 57$ in cyclohexane¹), it is blue-shifted compared to that observed in other tetra-azanaphthalenes, namely 1,4,5,8-tetraazanaphthalene ($\lambda_{max} = 402$ nm with $\epsilon = 230$ in cyclohexane¹) and 1,4,5,8-tetraazanaphthalene ($\lambda_{max} = 387$ nm with $\epsilon = 84$ in cyclohexane¹). This may be due to pronounced 'through space' effect present in the other tetra-azanaphthalenes. The weak shoulder at 400 nm, clearly observable in the solid spectrum, is tentatively assigned as a (n, π^*) triplet state. The compound gives fluorescence at 370 nm (see later), thus eliminating the possibility of the weak shoulder being a forbidden $^1(n, \pi^*)$ state. The lowest $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ state of the corresponding hydrocarbon naphthalene lies at 470 nm.

In order to study the polarisation of the $^1(n, \pi^*)$ band, we have tried to grow neat crystal of suitable dimension, but failed. We, however, were able to prepare mixed crystal with naphthalene. Naphthalene crystal belongs to the monoclinic system ($P2_1/a$) with unit cell dimension, $a = 8.235$ Å, $b = 6.003$ Å, $c = 8.658$ Å and $\beta = 122.55^\circ$ (Ref. 16). The monoclinic structure of naphthalene is characterised by a close packing of the molecules in the ab layer; repetition of these layers by translation along the c -axis is less dense, which gives rise to perfect cleavage of naphthalene along the (001) plane. The mixed crystal was cut through the cleavage plane, and the absorption spectra, both unpolarised and polarised, of the mixed crystal are shown in Fig. 2. Since the cleavage plane of naphthalene is perpendi-

cular to the molecular plane, the polarisation clearly shows that the $^1(n, \pi^*)$ transition is predominantly polarised perpendicular to the molecular plane. This cannot, however, suggest conclusively whether the band is electric-dipole-allowed or a forbidden one with borrowed intensity from nearby allowed $^1(n, \pi^*)$ transition.

Though a possibility of two close-lying $^1(n, \pi^*)$ states in PP is predicted (see Discussion) as in the case of other tetra-azanaphthalenes⁴, the absorption data is insufficiently resolved to throw light on this issue.

Emission: If PP is excited near 300-340 nm in the solid state (microcrystals packed in a thin quartz tube) or in different solvents at 77 K, weak emissions peaking at 370 and 500 nm have been observed (Fig. 3). Both emissions have the same excitation spectrum which corresponds very well to the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1(n, \pi^*)$ transition. The emission band having maximum intensity at 370 nm is assigned as

Fig. 3. Emission spectra at 77 K: (1) of microcrystal ($\lambda_{exc} = 300$ nm), (2) in methylcyclohexane ($\lambda_{exc} = 300$ nm), and (3) in THF/n-octane mixture ($\lambda_{exc} = 395$ nm).

the emission from the lowest (n, π^*) singlet state for the following reasons. (i) The emission band shows a mirror-image relationship with the $S_0 \rightarrow S_1(n, \pi^*)$ transition. (ii) The life-time of the emission is found to be $(15 \pm 5) \times 10^{-9}$ s in the solid state at 77 K. It is longer than the estimated lifetime of $^1(n, \pi^*)$ state, and of course, very short for a triplet state. If one allows for the possibility of non-radiative processes, it may be corresponded with the $^1(n, \pi^*)$ state, the radiative life-time of which is estimated to be of the order of 10^{-8} s.

Though the emission band having maximum intensity at 500 nm is almost structureless unlike other azanaphthalenes, it closely resembles what has been observed in the case of phthalazine⁵. The long life-time of the emission ($\approx 5 \times 10^{-8}$ s) measured

in the solid state at 77 K clearly establishes that the emission state is of triplet (π, π^*) nature. The decrease of the life-time in comparison with that of the parent hydrocarbon or of phthalazine ($\tau = 0.54 \text{ s}^9$) is an obvious indication of mixing of $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ state with $^3, ^1(n, \pi^*)$ states in the molecule. This may be the reason for the lack of phosphorescence in hydrocarbon solutions as has been noted in the case of phthalazine¹⁷ or in the case of cinnoline¹⁵.

The emission spectra observed were found to be independent of the excitation energy, concentration of the sample and time, showing that the second emission band is not due to any excimer formation or due to any photoproduct. The optical density of the 350 nm absorption band does not change after excitation indicating no significant photochemical decomposition during excitation.

Discussion

The transition probability for the ISC process $S_1 \rightarrow T_1$ is, according to the theory of radiationless process^{18, 19}, proportional to $|\langle S_1 | H_{S.O.} | T_1 \rangle|^2$, El-Sayed¹⁰ has found that

$$\frac{|\langle S^1(n, \pi^*) | H_{S.O.} | T^k(\pi, \pi^*) \rangle|^2}{|\langle S^1(n, \pi^*) | H_{S.O.} | T^1(n, \pi^*) \rangle|^2} \approx 10^8 \frac{|\langle S^1(n, \pi^*) | H_{S.O.} | T^1(n, \pi^*) \rangle|^2}{|\langle S^1(n, \pi^*) | H_{S.O.} | T^1(n, \pi^*) \rangle|^2}$$

where, $H_{S.O.}$ is the spin-orbit coupling operator and $S^1(n, \pi^*)$, $T^1(n, \pi^*)$, $T^k(\pi, \pi^*)$ and $S^k(\pi, \pi^*)$ are the pure spin Born-Oppenheimer states. It is, therefore, expected that the ISC rate in PP, where the lowest triplet has been identified as the (π, π^*) triplet state, should be very fast if one considers only the lowest B.O. triplet state in discussing the ISC process. The recent PMDR experiments²⁰ have, however, indicated that in N-heterocyclic compounds ISC processes between the $^1(n, \pi^*)$ and $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ states are, in general, only about 20 times faster instead of the estimated 10^8 times, than those between states of the same electronic type. The possible explanations for the occurrence of a (n, π^*) fluorescence in PP and hence relatively lower ISC rate [$S_1(n, \pi^*) \rightarrow T_1(\pi, \pi^*)$] are suggested below.

The planar molecule²¹ PP belongs to D_{2h} point group. The symmetrical and antisymmetrical linear combinations of n_1 to n_4 (n-orbitals on four nitrogen atoms) give rise to the following four n-orbitals of symmetry a_g, b_{2u}, b_{3u} and b_{1g} in PP (axes convention and atom numbering being given in Fig. 1; Z-axis being perpendicular to the molecular plane),

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_1(a_g) &= (n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + n_4)^{1/2} \\ \phi_2(b_{2u}) &= (n_1 - n_2 + n_3 - n_4)^{1/2} \\ \phi_3(b_{3u}) &= (n_1 + n_2 - n_3 - n_4)^{1/2} \\ \phi_4(b_{1g}) &= (n_1 - n_2 - n_3 + n_4)^{1/2} \end{aligned}$$

The top-most n-orbitals $\phi_4(b_{1g})$ and $\phi_2(b_{2u})$ should be of comparable energy because the groups (N_1, N_2) and (N_3, N_4) are well separated from each other. The lowest unoccupied orbitals should be

antisymmetric π^* with b_{2g} symmetry as in the case of naphthalene (using the same axes (convention)). Thus, the four (n, π^*) singlet states (considering the transition to the lowest π^* orbital) will be

$$^1B_{3g}[\phi_4(b_{1g}) \rightarrow \pi^*(b_{2g})], \quad ^1A_u[\phi_2(b_{2u}) \rightarrow \pi^*(b_{2g})],$$

$$^1B_{1u}[\phi_3(b_{3u}) \rightarrow \pi^*(b_{2g})] \text{ and } ^1B_{2g}[\phi_1(a_g) \rightarrow \pi^*(b_{2g})].$$

Among these, $^1A_g \rightarrow ^1B_{3g}$ and $^1A_g \rightarrow ^1A_u$ should have almost the same transition energy, their relative positions being determined by electron repulsion integrals. The other two transitions will be of higher energy. The orbital part of the lowest (π, π^*) triplet state in PP can be taken as of B_{2u} symmetry as observed by Hochstrasser and Lower²² in the case of the corresponding hydrocarbon, naphthalene. (It may be noted that they have used a different axes convention, where the symmetry of the orbital part of the lowest triplet is B_{1u}).

The spin-orbit coupling matrix between $^1(n, \pi^*)$ and $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ will exist only if $\langle ^1(n, \pi^*) | H_{S.O.} | ^3(\pi, \pi^*) \rangle$, i.e. $\langle \Gamma^1(n, \pi^*) | \Gamma(R_x, R_y, R_z) | \Gamma^3(\pi, \pi^*) \rangle$ contain Γ_1 , where Γ_1 is the totally symmetric representation of the point group². The three irreducible representations corresponding to the rotations R_x, R_y and R_z in D_{2h} point group are B_{3g}, B_{2g} and B_{1g} , respectively.

If the lowest (n, π^*) transition in PP is $^1A_g \rightarrow ^1B_{3g}$, the spin-orbit coupling matrix $\langle ^1\psi_{B_{3g}}(n, \pi^*) | H_{S.O.} | ^3\psi_{B_{2u}}(\pi, \pi^*) \rangle$ will vanish, since $H_{S.O.}$ is of g-symmetry. Thus, though the $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ state lies below the $^1(n, \pi^*)$ singlet, ISC rate will be small owing to the symmetry restriction allowing the (n, π^*) fluorescence to compete successfully with the non-radiative process. If one, however, assigns the lowest (n, π^*) singlet as 1A_u state, the only non-vanishing spin-orbit coupling matrix is $\langle ^1\psi_{A_u}(n, \pi^*) | L_y \cdot S_y | ^3\psi_{B_{2u}}(\pi, \pi^*) \rangle$, since L_y belongs to B_{2g} and $B_{2g} \cdot B_{2g} = A_u$ (the other two components of L.S. will give vanishing matrix elements). This matrix element can be broken down into matrix element over molecular orbitals of type $\langle n_{m.o.} | L_y | \pi_{m.o.} \rangle$, which can further be written in terms of atomic orbitals at the same N-centres, i.e. $\sum C_i \langle n_i | L_y | p_i \rangle$, where i runs over the N-atoms. If one takes into account the relative orientations of n_i, L_y and p_i , it is easy to see that each of the matrix elements $\langle n_i | L_y | p_i \rangle$ will be small in comparison with such one-centred terms in pyridine or pyridazine. Moreover, the π -electron in this case is extensively delocalised making the C_i 's on the N-atoms small. The net result is that the overall S.O. coupling between the particular $^1(n, \pi^*)$ state and the particular $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ state will be small leading to slow ISC rate and thus, fluorescence. Similar arguments in the case of phthalazine (point group being C_{2v}) where the lowest $^1(n, \pi^*)$ is of A_2 symmetry⁷ and the lowest $^3(\pi, \pi^*)$ is of B_2 symmetry²³ show that $\langle ^1(n, \pi^*) | H_{S.O.} | ^3(\pi, \pi^*) \rangle$ does not vanish.

Though absorption and emission data observed are unable to identify the symmetry of the lowest $^1(n, \pi^*)$ state in PP, the above discussion suggests

that the ISC rate will be low, more so when the lowest state is $^1B_{3g}$. A high resolution (<4 K spectral analysis) of the polarisation of the vibronic bands will be of great significance in this regard.

An alternative explanation, based on the spacing and ordering of levels, rather than on symmetry, may also be relevant. The ordering and the spacing of the observed singlet and triplet states of different orbital nature in pyridazinopyridazine, *i.e.* $^3(n,\pi^*)$ $\langle^3(n,\pi^*)|c\rangle$ $\langle^1(n,\pi^*)|1\rangle$, are very similar to those observed in 9,10-diazaphenanthrene¹³, another pyridazine derivative which fluoresces. Shimakura *et al.*²⁴ have explained the occurrence of (n,π) fluorescence and the lower ISC rate in 9,10-diazaphenanthrene on the basis of a four-electronic state model (the initial singlet, the final and two lowest intermediate triplet states); the rate constant for ISC from the lowest vibronic level of the lowest excited singlet, $|a\rangle$ to the manifold of vibronic levels of the lowest excited triplet state $\{|1\rangle\}$, assumed to be quasi-continuous, has been formulated by means of a Green function technique. The results of their model calculation show that the presence of the intermediate triplet state $|c\rangle$ in near resonance with the initial singlet $|a\rangle$, decreases the value of ISC rate constant through interference effect between the direct and indirect pathways. The conclusion is based on a model calculation with $E_a - E_b = 1000 \text{ cm}^{-1} \sim 3000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $V_{ab} \approx V_{ac} \approx 1 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Now, in PP containing many interacting non-bonding centres, the presence of a higher (n,π^*) triplet T_3 (corresponding to (n,π^*) singlet hidden under the $^1(n,\pi^*)$ bond) close to the $S_1(n,\pi^*)$ singlet is not unexpected. In this case also, $E_a - E_b$ $[=E_{S_1(n,\pi^*)} - E_{T_3(n,\pi^*)}] \approx 3000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and both V_{ab} (*i.e.* $V_{S_1T_3}$) and V_{ac} (*i.e.* $V_{S_1T_3}$) would be very small because all the states S_1 , T_3 and T_3 are of the (n,π^*) type (in general, $(n,\pi^*) |H_{S_0}|(n,\pi^*) \approx 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$). The result of the model calculation of Shimakura should, therefore, have qualitative significance for the case of PP also. This means that the ISC rate constant would be low allowing the (n,π^*) radiative fluorescence, the radiative life-time being fairly short, to compete effectively with it.

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